

ISic2713

I.Sicily inscription 2713

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (Cipollino)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15568

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. []

1. [---] καὶ []N[---]

2. ΝΕΩ[ἔζησε]ν ἔτη [---τό]

3. πος κοινός ἐστίν [] [] [] [---]

4. ἀμφοτέρωι χρησιανθ[ὶ ---]

Apparatus

Text after Griesheimer 1996 (line numbering amended)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645133

PHI 333380

Bibliography

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